

Engineering and physico-chemical properties of soils of deltaic region of West Bengal. Part-I [Physical (index and engineering) properties]

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Abstract : Soil has multifarious uses and can be studied from various points of view like agronomy, construction, environmental purifier, pollution etc. The different physical (index and engineering) properties of soils like moisture content, dry density, porosity, void-ratio, cohesion, compressibility, Atterberg limits like liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), plasticity etc. of soils of the deltaic region of West Bengal were studied. The values are important in understanding the physical properties of soils and sub-soils in the deltaic region and their suitability for engineering purposes.

Keywords : Atterberg limits, deltaic region, engineering properties, plasticity, soil, West Bengal.

Soil is essential for the basic needs of human being like housing, construction of roads, bridges, factories, power houses, dams etc. to meet the various demands of modern age. Naturally, the studies on the mechanical properties of soil are of great importance¹.

Soil is also the supporting medium for most forms of life and is the essential plant growth medium^{2,3}. Physical and chemical properties of soils are very much relevant to agricultural chemists for plant growth and soil management²⁻⁴.

Soil is ultimate repository or sink of all wastes coming from atmosphere, hydrosphere and biosphere. Soil pollution is on the increase due to man-made activities like indiscriminate disposal of wastes and toxic substances from industries, power houses, agricultural run-off containing fertilizers and pesticides makes menacing soil pollution⁵.

Attempts have been made to study the engineering (mechanical) and physico-chemical properties of soils of the active delta region of West Bengal with a view to correlate the engineering, physico-chemical and agronomic properties of soil. The results of the engineering properties of soils in deltaic regions are presented in Part-I of the communication.

Experimental

Sample collection^{6,7} :

Soil samples from different sites and from the desired depths were collected either by direct excavation or by boring (diameter of the hole being 100–150 mm, in general), by suitable method like auger, wash boring etc. Usually (1' × 1' × 1') box samples were collected after direct excavation or 3–4" diameter. 1–2' or more long undisturbed soil samples were collected, sealed with wax to prevent moisture loss and sent to laboratory for testing.

The water content, specific gravity were determined in the usual way. Atterberg limit tests were usually done on fine grained soils in which fines (silt + clay) are more than 50% (determined in the way described elsewhere)⁸. For the determination of liquid limit test, the soil passing 0.425 mm sieve is taken. In a standard liquid limit apparatus a soil pat is made and by a tool a groove of standard dimension is cut. Then the device is operated and number of blows is counted when the groove is closed (due to flow of the soil) for a distance 12 mm. At different moisture contents, blow numbers are different. From a semi log plot of moisture content vs blow number the liquid limit is obtained as the moisture content corresponding to 25 blows.

The method of determination of other engineering properties like undrained apparent cohesion (C_u , in kg/

cm²), compression index (C_c) and $C - \phi$ values (C = cohesion and ϕ = angle of shearing resistance) etc. were described elsewhere⁹.

Results and discussion

The different physical and engineering properties determined are given below :

Physical properties¹ :

(i) Water content or moisture content (m/c) :

It is the ratio of weight to water to the weight of soil (W_S) in a giving mass of soil. Generally, natural samples are taken. The water content in terms of percentage is expressed as

$$\% \text{ moisture content } (m/c) = \frac{W_T - W_S}{W_S} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Usually the weight of a definite mass of soil sample (W_T) is determined accurately. The sample is then kept in an air oven (105–110 °C) for 24 h and W_S is determined in the usual way.

(ii) Specific gravity (G) :

The specific gravity of a soil is the ratio of the weight (W_S) in air of a given volume of soil particles to the weight (W_W) in air of an equal volume of distilled water at a temperature of 4 °C.

$$G = \frac{W_S}{W_W} \quad (2)$$

(iii) Unit weight (γ_b) :

The unit weight or bulk density of a soil mass is defined as its weight per unit volume :

$$\gamma_b = \frac{W}{V} \text{ g/cc} \quad (3)$$

(iv) Dry density (γ_s) :

The dry density is the weight of solids per unit of total volume (V_T) (prior to drying) of the soil mass :

$$\gamma_s = \frac{W_S}{V_T} \quad (4)$$

(v) Void ratio (e) :

It is the ratio of the void volume (V_V) to the solid volume (V_S) of a given soil sample, i.e.

$$e = \frac{V_V}{V_S} \quad (5)$$

(vi) Porosity (n) :

The porosity, n , of a given soil sample is the ratio of the void volume (V_V) to the total volume (V_T) of the soil mass.

$$n = \frac{V_V}{V_T} = \frac{e}{1+e} \quad (6)$$

(vii) Degree of saturation (S) :

The degree of saturation S , indicates the percentage of the void volume which is filled with water.

$$S = \frac{V_W}{V_V} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

A value of $S = 0$ indicates a dry soil and $S = 100\%$ indicates a saturated soil. A value between 0–100% indicates a partially saturated soil.

Index and engineering properties :

Atterberg limits and plasticity chart :

Consistency is meant by the relative ease with which a clayey soil can be deformed. A soil is termed as soft, medium or stiff or hard depending on the deformability of a soil i.e. a soft soil is easily deformed and a stiff soil is tough to deform. Atterberg (1911), divided the entire range from liquid to solid state into four stages or limits viz. the liquid state, the plastic state, the semi-solid state and the solid state in terms of water content. The Atterberg limits which are useful for engineering purpose are liquid limit, plastic limit and shrinkage limit. The limit tests are usually done on fine grained soils in which fines (silt + clay) are more than 50%.

(a) Liquid limit :

It is the water content corresponding to the arbitrary limit between liquid and plastic states of consistency of soil. It is the minimum water content at which the soil is still in liquid state and possesses very little shear strength (20–25 g/cm) against flowing.

(b) Plastic limit :

It is the arbitrary limit between the plastic and semi-solid states of a soil. It is defined as the minimum water content at which a thread (made of the soil) of about 3 mm diameter just begins to crumble when rolled.

(c) Shrinkage limit :

It is the maximum water content at which a reduction in water content will not cause a decrease in volume of a soil mass. It is the lowest water content at which the soil is still saturated.

(d) Plasticity index ($PI = LL - PL$) :

It is the range of consistency within which a soil exhibits plastic properties.

(e) Plasticity :

It is the property of a soil that allows it to be deformed rapidly without rupture, without rebound and without volume change.

(f) Activity :

It is given as $\bar{A} = PI/Clay\%$. The soils with \bar{A} less than 0.75 are termed as inactive, the value in between 0.75 to 1.25 means normally active and above 1.25 means highly active. Of course, these values are arbitrary. Soils, with kaolinite as dominant mineral are inactive i.e. show less plasticity and the soils with montmorillonite as dominant mineral are highly active i.e. show higher plasticity for similar clay content. Natural clay is a mixture of different clay minerals. The resultant clay contributes to the actual behavior of the clayey soil.

(g) Plasticity chart :

Laboratory classification of fine grained soils is done with the help of plasticity chart shown in the Fig. 1.

The A-line for $PI = 0.73 (LL - 20)$ divides inorganic clays from silts and clays. Fine grained soils are divided into groups as M-inorganic silts, C-inorganic clays and O-organic clays. Based on the values of liquid limit these are further subdivided as soils of low compressibility, L ($LL < 35$), intermediate compressibility, I ($LL = 35-50$) and high compressibility, H ($LL > 50$).

The engineering parameters which characterize the soils are given in Table 1 and Table 2. The engineering properties of soils determined are given in Table 3. The engineering properties depend on clay%, clay mineral, moisture content etc.

The physical and engineering properties of soils in West Bengal have been relatively little studied though the studies on the agricultural and other mineralogical aspects of soils have attracted wide attention.

Fig. 1. Plasticity chart.

Table 1. Some common classification of soils and their characteristic properties

Major division	Group symbol	Typical names	Dry strength	Dialatancy	Toughness	Compressibility and expansion	Drainage characteristics	Unit dry density (g/cc)
Sils and clay with medium compressibility, liquid limit > 35 and < 50 (more than half material is smaller than < 75 μm sieve size)	MI	Inorganic silts, silty or clayey fine sand or clayey silts of medium plasticity	Low	Quick to slow	None	Low to medium	Fair to poor	1.44–2.08
	CI	Inorganic clays, gravelly clays, sandy clays, silty clays of medium plasticity	Medium to high	None	Medium	Medium	Practically impervious	1.44–2.08
	OI	Organic silts and organic silty clays of medium plasticity	Low to medium	Slow	Low	Medium to high	Poor	1.44–1.68
Sils and clays with high compressibility, liquid limit > 50	CH	Inorganic clays of high plasticity, fat clays	High to very high	None	High	High	Practically impervious	1.44–1.84

Deddal¹⁰, Ghosh and Gupta¹¹, Das and Parua¹² reported the engineering properties of soils from different parts of West Bengal. Lambe¹³ in his classical paper stressed on the need of studying fundamentals of the engineering behavior of clay minerals which are equally applicable for soils containing silt and clay. Studies on compacted clay can be of immediate practical value as well as of value to the basic understanding of the fine grained soils. Compacted clays both with and without stabilizers are being used more and more in engineering works.

According to Lambe¹³, the structure of a clay determines its properties and the structure and the different electrical and chemical forces in soils must be considered in order to understand the fundamentals of soil behaviour. The engineering properties of the alluvial soils of the southern parts of West Bengal and particularly of Sundarbans have been little studied. In recent years, increasing interest has been observed for the development of South Bengal and particularly of Sundarbans as it has the potentiality of development of tourism and resource generation.

Soil properties of the deltaic region :

Soil formation is the result of long drawn weathering processes comprising of different physical methods of disintegration and different chemical interaction. Soils

may be residual, alluvial, marine etc. But the present study is concerned with mostly alluvial soils in the active delta region of West Bengal.

The southern parts of North and South 24-Parganas (including Sundarban areas) and the southern and eastern fringes of Medinipur constitute the active delta region as delta building (despite of stray erosion) is still going on in this region. It is actually the flood plains of the river Ganga and its tributaries and their continuation [*cf.* the flood plains and delta regions of the Mississippi River Valley, The Nile River Valley, The Indus, Brahmaputra, Hwang Ho and the Amazon river valleys. Areas of delta sediments are subject to flood control and drainage areas are very productive and important for agricultural point of view and are used extensively for the production of Wetland rice]¹⁴.

The Ganga, its tributaries and spill channels draining a huge area interact with tides near the outfall to the sea and deposit soils carried by the river streams and the tidal waves under favourable conditions. Evidence of two environments of deposition viz. flood plain or Backswamp environment and Meander Belt environment is noticed in the soil horizons/layers. According to Stoke's law, $v = kr^2$ (v = the rate of settling of particle in a soil suspension, r = radius of soil particle and k is a constant), coarser particles settle rapidly and finer ones slowly. Hence the

Table 2. Characteristics of soil based on engineering properties

Parameter	Value	Soil	Compressibility
(1) C_u (in kg/cm^2)	0-0.35	Soft	High
(undrained apparent cohesion)	0.35-9.70	Medium stiff	Medium
	0.70-1.5	Stiff	Low
	> 1.5	Very stiff	
(1) C_c (Compression index)	< 0.1		Low
	0.1-0.4		Low to medium
	0.4-0.7		Medium to high
	> 0.7		Very high
(3) C - ϕ relationship	$(C = \text{cohesion and } \phi = \text{shearing resistance})$		
	(i) for saturated clay $\phi = 0$		
	(ii) for sand $C = 0, \phi > 25^\circ$		
	$\phi < 32$		Loose
	$\phi = 32-36^\circ$		Medium
	$\phi = 36-40^\circ$		Dense
	$\phi > 40^\circ$		Very dense
	(for partially saturated clay both C and ϕ important)		
(4) LL (Liquid limit)	< 35		Low
	35-50		Intermediate
	> 50		High
(5) m/c (Moisture content)	Near LL	Soft (DD low)	
	Between LL and PL	Medium (DD medium)	
	Near PL	Stiff (DD high)	

PL = Plastic Limit.

former environment provides time for settling of finer soils while the latter causes deposition of sandy soils. The sequential change like course shift etc. common in a deltaic plain is the cause of alternate layers of sand and clay at a particular site.

Information on the clay mineralogy of soils is essential for evolving better management practices for the soils and for better understanding their engineering and physical properties responsible for construction and agricultural purposes. However, no work on soils structure and soil mineralogy had been carried out.

In soil the colloids (inorganic clay minerals with organic humus content having large surface area and surface activity, high water holding capacity) are the most active fraction which monitor the fertility status of a soil being enclosed within a skeleton frame work of the fraction of the sand (have poor water holding capacity, good drainage and aeration capacity). The presence of clay in a soil gives it a fine texture and slow water and air movement. Clay also controls the engineering properties like liquid limit, plastic limit etc.

The soils in the active delta region though not uniform but can be regarded to be composed of mainly illite and smectite with other minerals like vermiculite, chlorite, kaolinite, etc. in varying proportions.

The physical and mechanical properties of soils at different sites and depths are presented in Table 3.

The soils formed by the particles of 50% or more finer than 0.02 mm (20 μm) size having varying percentages of clay are cohesive. Of these clays normally consolidated clays are soft to medium and over consolidated clays are of medium to stiff consistency (the relative ease with which soil can be deformed). Such plastic soils are found at some depths at Rajnagar, Kakdwip, Shibpur, Namkhana, Jharkhali, Basanti, Jagatpur, Diamond Harbour, Tentulia etc.

Often soils having a good percentage of clay (very high) and fine and medium silt are encountered. The soils are lowly plastic and of low to medium consistency and strength. Such soils are found at some depths at Digha Sea Beach, Basanti, Kachuberia, Jharkhali.

Table 3. Engineering and physical properties of soils of active deltaic region of West Bengal

Sample no.	Site	Geographical region	Ground elevation from sea level (m)	Depth below GL (m)	Particle size distribution (%)			Index properties			DD (g/cc)	MC (%)	Shear parameters			
					Sand	Silt	Clay	LL	PL	United soil classification			Cu (kg/cm ²)	C	ϕ	K (cm/s)
Jag-1	Jagatpur, 24-Parganas (N)	6-7	3.0	4.4-4.6	1.1	63.1	35.8	—	—	—	1.20	49.9	0.22	0.19	6.0	0.50
Jag-2	Jagatpur, 24-Parganas (N)	6-7	—	6.4-6.6	73.0	27.0	—	—	—	1.51	33.9	—	0.05	20.0	—	—
Jag-3	Jagatpur, 24-Parganas (N)	6-7	—	7.4-7.6	87.0	13.0	—	—	—	1.53	31.2	—	—	—	—	—
Bas-1	Basanti, 24-Parganas (S)	7	4.4	2.8-3.0	9.5	75.0	15.5	—	—	1.26	33.0	0.20	—	—	—	—
Bas-2	Basanti, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	6.0-6.2	14.0	56.2	29.8	—	—	1.30	37.2	0.34	—	—	—	—
Bas-3	Basanti, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	8.0-8.5	36.0	60.0	4.0	—	Non plastic	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Bas-4	Basanti, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	16.1-16.4	30.0	60.6	9.4	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Jha-1	Jharkhali, 24-Parganas (S)	7	2.1	1.8-2.0	1.5	65.3	33.2	51	26	CH	1.37	37.3	—	0.22	6.0	0.32
Jha-2	Jharkhali, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	2.6-2.8	8.0	80.6	11.4	33	25	OI-MI	1.57	30.0	—	—	—	0.10
Dho-1	Dhosa, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	2.0	2.9-3.1	63.7	33.1	3.2	—	—	—	1.41	30.6	—	—	25.0	—
Dho-2	Dhosa, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	3.8-4.0	78.0	22.0	—	—	Non plastic	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dho-3	Dhosa, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	4.8-5.0	65.0	32.9	2.1	—	—	1.36	29.0	—	0.21	18.0	—	—
Dho-4	Dhosa, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	5.8-6.0	97.0	3.0	—	—	—	1.36	30.7	—	—	—	—	—
Dia-1	Diamond Harbour, 24-Parganas (S)	6	2.8	3.0-3.2	9.0	56.8	34.2	46	26	CI	1.35	37.3	—	0.3	8.0	—
Dia-2	Diamond Harbour, 24-Parganas (S)	6	—	4.0-4.5	5.2	53.9	40.9	56	29	CH	1.20	40.0	—	—	—	8×10^{-8}
Dia-3	Diamond Harbour, 24-Parganas (S)	6	—	5.0-5.2	5.0	50.6	4.4	58	29	CH	1.14	50.8	—	—	—	—
Dia-4	Diamond Harbour, 24-Parganas (S)	6	—	7.0-7.2	10.1	60.1	29.8	43	24	CI	1.20	39.6	—	—	—	—

Table-3 (contd.)

Ten-1	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	2.5	1.1-1.3	6.0	66.5	27.5	47	24.7	CI	1.42	31.9	0.22	0.20	3.0
Ten-2	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	3.1-3.3	6.9	66.0	27.1	46.6	22.8	CI	1.49	30.2	0.28	—	—
Ten-3	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	4.1-4.3	15.6	68.1	16.3	37.0	26.7	MI-OI	1.49	24.1	0.40	—	—
Ten-4	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	5.1-5.3	22.6	66.5	10.9	30.2	29.3	MI-OI	1.28	38.2	0.19	0.18	6.0
Ten-5	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	7.1-7.3	93.5	6.5	—	—	—	Non plastic	1.48	34.8	—	—	30.0
Ten-6	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	8.1-8.3	92.8	7.2	—	—	—	Non plastic	1.42	3.12	—	—	18.5
Ten-7	Tentulia, 24-Parganas (S)	6-7	—	9.1-9.3	88.0	12.0	—	—	—	Non plastic	1.45	25.5	—	—	24.0
Raj-1	Rajnagar, 24-Parganas (S)	7	2.4	1.2-1.4	3.0	65.7	31.3	49	26	CI	1.40	30.0	—	—	3×10^{-7}
Raj-2	Rajnagar, 24-Parganas (S)	7	2.4	2.3-2.5	4.5	72.2	23.3	42	25	CI	1.47	30.0	—	0.13	5.0
Shi-1	Shibpur, 24-Parganas (S)	7	1.8	1.0-1.2	2.0	59.1	38.9	60	29	CH	1.32	37.0	—	—	1.1×10^{-6}
Shi-2	Shibpur, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	1.8-2.1	1.0	60.8	38.2	56	26	CH	1.36	40.0	—	0.14	3.5
Kac-1	Kachuberia, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	5.8-6.0	9.0	58.0	33.0	49	28	CI-OI-MI	1.30	45.8	0.15	—	—
Kac-2	Kachuberia, 24-Parganas (S)	7	—	8.2-8.4	48.0	42.0	10.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dig-1	Digha, Medinipur (E)	8	(-) 0.5	0.4-0.6	100.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dig-2	Digha, Medinipur (E)	8	—	6.6-6.8	18.8	76.0	5.2	—	—	Non plastic	—	32.8	—	—	—
Dig-3	Digha, Medinipur (E)	8	—	6.8-7.0	34.4	64.0	1.6	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Dig-4	Digha, Medinipur (E)	8	—	9.6-9.8	32.0	58.2	10.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

Soils having 50% or more particles with size greater than 0.02 mm (20 μm) i.e. high coarse silt and sand percentage with trace or no clay, are non-plastic and non-cohesive. These sandy soils are found at some depths at Tentulia, Jagatpur, Kumrakhali, Digha Sea Beach. In some cases the sands are clean i.e. free of silt and clay. It is interesting to note that the fine sand is the dominant sand size.

Dry density (DD g/cc), moisture content, permeability :

From Table 3, it is apparent that the soils containing high percentages of silt have moderate DD values. Moisture content of the soils are medium. Apparently pore space of the soils are medium. The coefficient of permeability or permeability of soils was measured at few places. The low *K*-values (cm/s) suggest that the soils are impermeable indicating poor recharging possibility of the aquifers in this region. Due to heavy withdrawal of water from underground using shallow pumps for irrigation purpose and poor recharging possibilities, the concentration of 'As' has increased alarmingly in the underground water. This may be regarded to be one of the major causes of 'As'-pollution in the deltaic region.

Sub-soils at different sites :

Fig. 2 gives the sub-soil conditions at different sites in the region. These plots are basically the results from

cone penetration done at these sites. Soil samples were collected from different depths. Allowable bearing capacity (ABC) values are evaluated from cone penetration tests taking a factor of safety equal to 4.

The soil is classified as normally consolidated clay (NC) [i.e. it exists in a natural load system which is maximum since its origin] or an over consolidated clay (OC) [i.e. it exists under a load which is less than a higher load the clay experienced in the geological past]. The top soils are generally found to be cohesive, silty clay-clayey silt and are basically over consolidated (OC) to different degrees. In comparison to normally consolidated soil, an OC soil is stiffer, the stiffness being function of the degree of over consolidation. In natural deposits of alluvial origin, the surface soils experience wetting and drying over the years and due to ground water table fluctuation, an over consolidation effect is induced in the soil system but at some depths below normal ground level the soil may be normally consolidated (NC). In NC soil moisture content is nearer the liquid limit and in OC soil it is nearer to the plastic limit, in general.

The OC effect is not prominent (inferred from values) at Basanti, Jharkhali, Diamond Harbour and Kachuberia.

Up to the depth explored, a deep deposit of NC soils exist at Basanti and Jharkhali, less plasticity is observed

Fig. 2. Typical penetration test plots at different sites in active delta region and coastal areas of West Bengal.

in a few cases due to small percentage of clay. Non-cohesive soils are expected to be present below the clayey deposits at Jagatpur, Diamond Harbour, Tentulia, Rajnagar, Shibpur, Kachuberia. The non-cohesive soils (sand, silty sand or sandy silt) are of loose to medium density but have high bearing value. At Dhosa, the sub-soils are more or less sandy (medium dense) with some finer particles at the top. Fine sand of loose to medium density is present at the top few metres of Digha Sea Beach with sandy silt and small percentages of clay in the lower layers. These soils are cohesive but lowly plastic.

Remarks for engineering constructions :

The engineering structures should be founded on the sub-structures capable of distributing load through the existing sub-soils. The sub-structures or foundations should be designed considering the sub-soils to be a deep deposit of normally consolidated clays. However, further soil investigations should be done to get better details.

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